

I wonder about...DNA

(adapted from <http://nexusresearchgroup.com/fun-science/extracting-dna.htm>)

If you take a seed away from its parent plant, even as far as the other side of the world, how does the seed know what it should grow into? Think about your own body. Muscles are made up of muscle cells, the skin is made up of skin cells, and so on. How does a skin cell know how to be a skin cell? If it is true that you can't make a cake without a recipe, then you can't build a living thing without a plan. Cells carry their own set of instructions, a sort of recipe, to follow. Is it true that this recipe, DNA, is easily extracted by investigators of crime scenes? How could we discover some evidence that this is true for ourselves?

Here is a draft copy of one possible learning activity...

To extract your own DNA (protocol developed by Michael Fenton)

- To a 1/2 cup of water dissolve about 1/2 teaspoon of salt and add a squirt of dish-washing detergent. Save this for step 3
- Swirl about 25 mls of water around your mouth for 30 seconds. This removes some cheek cells. Spit into a disposable cup
- Add about 2cm of the fluid to a test-tube (or a Fuji film canister) and add about 1cm of the saline/detergent solution. Invert gently 3 or 4 times to mix well (but you don't want a lot of froth). This will break open the many cheek cells you spat out, releasing the DNA message that each cell must carry.
- Layer on top some ice cold ethanol (or methanol). Strands of DNA will be seen where the two layers meet. Hook out the strands of DNA that form with a glass hook (or one made from a plastic twist-tie) by slowly dipping up and down through the two layers.

DNA on glass rod

Deoxyribo**N**ucleic **A**cid (DNA) is the chemical message cells read to know what to do. Change the message and you change the type of cell...change the cell and you change the organ...change the organ and you change the whole organism. If the DNA from a luminescent jellyfish is inserted into the DNA plan of a mouse it could glow in the dark. This has actually been done! This creature is now both jellyfish and mouse...a totally new lifeform through genetic engineering.

Questions:

- Where in the cell do you think DNA is located?

- What is the significance of the DNA code being the same in all life forms?
What does 'genetic engineering' mean?
- How could an animal or human be cloned?
- What is the significance of DNA in the solving of crimes?
- Are there some chemical test that could be done on your sample to confirm the presence of DNA?

What did we do today?

In general, if you want to work like a scientist, you often use the following investigative approaches...

- Modelling
- Classifying and identifying
- Pattern seeking
- Making things or developing systems
- Observing
- Fair testing (the Scientific Method)

Which of the approaches did you use in this exercise?
